

A VARIATIONAL MULTISCALE METHOD FOR THE SIMULATION OF POROUS MEDIA FLOW IN HIGHLY HETEROGENEOUS FORMATIONS

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ABSTRACT

We present a variational multiscale mixed finite element method for the solution of Darcy flow in porous media, in which the permeability field displays a multiscale character. The formulation is based on a multiscale split of the solution into coarse and subgrid scales. This decomposition is invoked in a variational setting that leads to a rigorous definition of a (global) coarse problem and a set of (local) subgrid problems. The method is locally conservative and employs a low-order approximation of pressure and velocity at both scales. The method is an extension of the numerical subgrid upscaling technique proposed by Arbogast. Specifically, it allows for subgrid communication across element interfaces, something that turns out to be essential for obtaining high-quality solutions. We illustrate the performance of the method on several synthetic cases, and conclude that the method is able to capture the global and local flow patterns accurately.

1. INTRODUCTION

The equations governing the flow of fluids in the subsurface (oil and gas reservoirs, confined aquifers, vadose zone, etc.) can, in many cases, be formulated in terms of a single “pressure” equation (of elliptic character) describing an overall mass balance, and “component” equations (of hyperbolic character) governing the differential displacement of each component [Aziz and Settari, 1979].

In this work, we concentrate on the numerical solution of a model pressure equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (-\mathbf{k}\nabla p) = f, \tag{1}$$

where the coefficient tensor \mathbf{k} is discontinuous, highly variable, and may present short and long correlation lengths. A number of approaches are currently being investigated for the numerical simulation of porous media flow with rough permeability fields. We can identify at least two main tracks: multiscale finite element methods and variational multiscale methods.

The multiscale finite element method was originally proposed by Hou and Wu [1997] for the solution of elliptic equations with rapidly oscillating coefficients. The main idea is to construct finite element basis functions which themselves are solutions to the elliptic operator inside each element and, therefore, capture small scale information. The method was analyzed in a series of subsequent papers (see, e.g. Efendiev et al. [2000]; Hou et al. [1999]). A mixed finite element version that guarantees local mass conservation at the element level was proposed by Chen and Hou [2002]. This work was recently extended in

a number of important ways by the Norwegian school [*Aarnes*, 2004; *Aarnes et al.*, 2005]. Inspired in the multiscale finite element method, *Jenny et al.* [2003] proposed a multiscale finite volume method that also preserves mass conservation at the coarse and fine scales.

The variational multiscale method was originally proposed by *Hughes* [1995]; *Hughes et al.* [1998] as an overarching framework for the solution of partial differential equations that exhibit multiscale phenomena (either due to small-scale heterogeneity or sharp features that cannot be captured on a coarse grid). The essence of the method is to perform a multiscale split of the solution into a coarse-scale part (that can be approximated on a coarse grid) and a subscale component. The multiscale split is invoked in a variational setting, which leads to a rigorous definition of a coarse-scale problem and a subgrid-scale problem. While an approximation (localization) of the subgrid problem is typically necessary, the framework offers a rigorous formulation for incorporating subgrid effects in the coarse scale equations. A mixed variant of the method, coined “numerical subgrid up-scaling” was developed independently by *Arbogast* [*Arbogast*, 2000, 2002, 2004; *Arbogast and Bryant*, 2002]. A thorough comparison of the different multiscale methods (as well as interesting extensions) has recently been presented in *Kippe et al.* [2006].

In this work, we adopt the variational multiscale framework to develop a locally conservative multiscale method that extends the method proposed by *Arbogast* [2002]. The main contribution is to relax the localization assumption needed to define the local subgrid problems. The proposed method leads to local mass conservation at both scales, and greatly enhances the ability to capture the multiscale character of the solution in problems without scale separation (that is, when the length-scales of heterogeneity and the coarse grid are comparable), while being a low-order method. The paper reflects the ideas first communicated by *Juanes* [2004] and further elaborated in *Juanes* [2005a,b].

2. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

2.1. Governing equations. We shall use the following model pressure equation:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = f \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (2)$$

where f is the source term, and \mathbf{u} is the total velocity given by Darcy’s law:

$$\mathbf{u} = -\mathbf{k}\nabla p. \quad (3)$$

The symbol \mathbf{k} is the permeability tensor and p is the pressure. In a more general setting (multiphase flow problems including gravity effects) \mathbf{k} is the total mobility tensor, and p is the flow potential. The permeability tensor is symmetric and positive definite. The components of \mathbf{k} are assumed to be bounded, but they may be highly discontinuous and display large anisotropy ratios. In this work we shall assume, however, that \mathbf{k} is a diagonal tensor. The pressure equation is supplemented with the following boundary conditions:

$$p = \bar{p} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_p, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \bar{u} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_u, \quad (5)$$

where $\Gamma_p \cap \Gamma_u = \emptyset$, $\Gamma_p \cup \Gamma_u = \partial\Omega$, and \mathbf{n} is the outward unit normal to the boundary. For expositional simplicity, and without loss of generality (see, e.g. [*Brezzi and Fortin*, 1991, Section IV.1]), we may take a homogeneous Neumann boundary condition:

$$\bar{u} = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_u. \quad (6)$$

2.2. Mixed variational formulation. We write Equations (2)–(3) in the following form:

$$\mathbf{k}^{-1}\mathbf{u} + \nabla p = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = f, \quad (8)$$

and introduce the following common functional spaces:

$$W \equiv L^2(\Omega) = \left\{ q : \int_{\Omega} |q|^2 \, d\Omega = \|q\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 < +\infty \right\}, \quad (9)$$

$$H(\operatorname{div}, \Omega) = \left\{ \mathbf{v} : \mathbf{v} \in (L^2(\Omega))^2, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \in L^2(\Omega) \right\}. \quad (10)$$

The space $L^2(\Omega)$ is the usual Sobolev space of square integrable functions in Ω . The space $H(\operatorname{div}, \Omega)$ is defined such that vectors belonging to this space admit a well-defined normal trace on $\partial\Omega$ [Brezzi and Fortin, 1991, Section III.1.1]. We will also make use of the following space:

$$V \equiv H_{0,u}(\operatorname{div}, \Omega) = \left\{ \mathbf{v} : \mathbf{v} \in H(\operatorname{div}, \Omega), \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_u \right\}. \quad (11)$$

Employing the usual inner-product and duality notation,

$$(q, p) \equiv (q, p)_{L^2(\Omega)} := \int_{\Omega} q p \, d\Omega, \quad q, p \in L^2(\Omega), \quad (12)$$

$$(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u}) \equiv (\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u})_{H(\operatorname{div}, \Omega)} := \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{u} \, d\Omega, \quad \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} \in H(\operatorname{div}, \Omega), \quad (13)$$

$$\langle \bar{u}, \bar{p} \rangle_{\Gamma} := \int_{\Gamma} \bar{u} \bar{p} \, d\Gamma, \quad \bar{u} \in H^{1/2}(\Gamma), \bar{p} \in H^{-1/2}(\Gamma), \quad (14)$$

we can express the problem given by Equations (7)–(8) with boundary conditions (4)–(6) in mixed variational form: Find $(\mathbf{u}, p) \in V \times W$ such that

$$(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{k}^{-1}\mathbf{u}) - (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}, p) = -\langle \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n}, \bar{p} \rangle_{\Gamma_p} \quad \forall \mathbf{v} \in V, \quad (15)$$

$$(w, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) = (w, f) \quad \forall w \in W. \quad (16)$$

It is well known that this problem has a unique solution [Brezzi and Fortin, 1991].

2.3. The mixed finite element method. The mixed variational formulation provides the basis for the mixed finite element method. Let $V_h \subset V$, and $W_h \subset W$ be finite dimensional subspaces of the corresponding continuum spaces, the discrete mixed finite element approximation of (15)–(16) reads: Find $(\mathbf{u}_h, p_h) \in V_h \times W_h$ such that

$$(\mathbf{v}_h, \mathbf{k}^{-1}\mathbf{u}_h) - (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h, p_h) = -\langle \mathbf{v}_h \cdot \mathbf{n}, \bar{p} \rangle_{\Gamma_p} \quad \forall \mathbf{v}_h \in V_h, \quad (17)$$

$$(w_h, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h) = (w_h, f) \quad \forall w_h \in W_h. \quad (18)$$

The spaces V_h and W_h cannot be chosen independently; they must satisfy a standard coercivity condition and the discrete inf-sup condition [Babuška, 1973; Brezzi, 1974]. The numerical solution of (17)–(18) invariably involves a partition \mathcal{T}_h of the domain Ω into nonoverlapping elements e_i , $\Omega = \bigcup_{i=1}^m e_i$. We shall understand this partition \mathcal{T}_h as the fine grid, on which the permeability \mathbf{k} is defined. For definiteness, we shall use a partition into rectangular elements, and associate the fine-scale velocity space with the lowest-order Raviart–Thomas space, RT_0 [Raviart and Thomas, 1977]. The corresponding pressure approximation is piecewise constant on the fine mesh \mathcal{T}_h .

3. THE VARIATIONAL MULTISCALE METHOD

The essence of the variational multiscale method [Hughes, 1995] is to perform a multi-scale split of the solution into a coarse-scale part (that can be approximated on a coarse grid) and a subscale component. The multiscale split is invoked in a variational setting, which leads to a rigorous definition of a coarse-scale problem and a subgrid-scale problem. By virtue of this decomposition, we acknowledge that the fine-scale details of the solution cannot be captured on a coarse grid. As it turns out, inaccuracies at the subgrid level may resonate, and produce a numerical solution that is *globally* polluted with errors.

Consider a coarse partition of the domain \mathcal{T}_H , and the decomposition of the solution:

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_H + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \quad (19)$$

$$p = p_H + \tilde{p}. \quad (20)$$

This decomposition is unique if we can express the original functional space $V \times W$ as the direct sum of two spaces, with:

$$V = V_H \oplus \tilde{V}, \quad (21)$$

$$W = W_H \oplus \tilde{W}, \quad (22)$$

where $V_H \times W_H$ is the space of coarse scales, and $\tilde{V} \times \tilde{W}$ is the space of subgrid scales. This decomposition allows us to split the continuum problem (15)–(16) into a coarse-scale problem and a subscale problem. Testing against coarse-scale test functions we obtain the coarse-scale problem: Find $(\mathbf{u}_H, p_H) \in V_H \times W_H$ such that

$$(\mathbf{v}_H, \mathbf{k}^{-1}\mathbf{u}_H) + (\mathbf{v}_H, \mathbf{k}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{u}}) - (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_H, p_H) - (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_H, \tilde{p}) = -\langle \mathbf{v}_H \cdot \mathbf{n}, \bar{p} \rangle_{\Gamma_p}, \quad (23)$$

$$(w_H, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_H) + (w_H, \nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}}) = (w_H, f). \quad (24)$$

for all $\mathbf{v}_H \in V_H$ and $w_H \in W_H$. Testing against the subscale test functions, and expressing the inner product as sums over coarse elements $E = 1, \dots, N_c$, we arrive at the subscale problem: Find $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \tilde{p}) \in \tilde{V} \times \tilde{W}$ such that

$$\sum_E \left[(\tilde{\mathbf{v}}, \mathbf{k}^{-1}\mathbf{u}_H)_E + (\tilde{\mathbf{v}}, \mathbf{k}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{u}})_E - (\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}, p_H)_E - (\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}, \tilde{p})_E \right] = - \sum_E \langle \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \cdot \mathbf{n}, \bar{p} \rangle_{\Gamma_{p,E}}, \quad (25)$$

$$\sum_E \left[(\tilde{w}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_H)_E + (\tilde{w}, \nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}})_E \right] = \sum_E (\tilde{w}, f)_E. \quad (26)$$

for all $\tilde{\mathbf{v}} \in \tilde{V}$ and $\tilde{w} \in \tilde{W}$. We make the following remarks:

- (1) So far, the solution obtained from the additive decomposition above is exact.
- (2) The formulation is residual based in the sense that if the coarse solution is the exact solution, the subscales vanish identically.
- (3) The subgrid-scale problem is an infinite dimensional, global problem. Therefore, in the form presented above, the complexity of the problem is the same as the original one.
- (4) For the formulation to be advantageous from a computational viewpoint, we need a judicious choice of the coarse and subgrid approximation spaces, as well as a good localization assumption that will decouple the global subgrid problem into a set of local problems. These two key issues are addressed in Sections 4 and 5, respectively.

4. CHOICE OF THE FINITE ELEMENT SPACES

The objective of the variational multiscale mixed finite element method (VMSMFE) is to provide an approximation to the fine-scale solution of (17)–(18), as the sum of a solution to a global coarse-scale problem and a set of local subgrid problems. More precisely, we construct the following approximation sequence:

$$\mathbf{u} \approx \mathbf{u}_h \approx \mathbf{u}_{H,h} = \mathbf{u}_H + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \quad (27)$$

$$p \approx p_h \approx p_{H,h} = p_H + \tilde{p}, \quad (28)$$

where $(\mathbf{u}, p) \in V \times W$, $(\mathbf{u}_h, p_h) \in V_h \times W_h$, $(\mathbf{u}_H, p_H) \in V_H \times W_H$, and $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \tilde{p}) \in \tilde{V} \times \tilde{W}$.

We assume, for simplicity, that the partitions \mathcal{T}_h (fine grid) and \mathcal{T}_H (coarse grid) are nested, and consist of rectangular elements. The target fine-scale approximation spaces are the lowest-order Raviart–Thomas space for the velocity, $V_h = RT_0(\mathcal{T}_h)$, and the space of piecewise constants for the pressure, $W_h = P_0(\mathcal{T}_h)$. We restrict our attention to coarse-scale velocity spaces that are compatible with a piecewise constant approximation of the pressure, $W_H = P_0(\mathcal{T}_H)$. The two obvious choices are $V_H = RT_0(\mathcal{T}_H)$ and the Brezzi–Douglas–Marini space of order 1, $V_H = BDM_1(\mathcal{T}_H)$ [Brezzi *et al.*, 1985]. Both spaces satisfy that $\text{div } V_H = W_H$. In contrast with the choice of Arbogast [2002, 2004], in this work we use the low-order $RT_0(\mathcal{T}_H)$ space. Of course, to mimic the fine-scale solution, the subgrid velocities are restricted to belong to the lowest-order Raviart–Thomas space on the fine grid within each coarse element, $RT_0(E_h)$.

5. LOCALIZATION OF THE SUBGRID PROBLEMS

The essential requirement in the construction of our multiscale method is that *the approximation be locally conservative at both scales*, that is, it must satisfy the discrete version of the mass conservation statement on each element of the coarse and fine grids.

This requirement leads to the condition:

$$(w_H, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_H)_E = (w_H, f)_E \quad \forall E \in \mathcal{T}_H, \quad (29)$$

or, equivalently, $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_H = \Pi_H f$ — the projection of the source term onto the space W_H of piecewise constants on the coarse grid. Substituting (29) in the coarse-scale equation (24) leads to

$$(w_H, \nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}})_E = 0 \quad \forall E \in \mathcal{T}_H. \quad (30)$$

Since w_H is constant on each element, we can use the divergence theorem to translate Equation (30) into the following *compatibility condition on the subgrid velocities*:

$$\boxed{\int_{\partial E} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad \forall E \in \mathcal{T}_H.} \quad (31)$$

Equation (31) is the essential condition that guarantees mass conservation at both scales, and allows to localize the subgrid-scale problem. Of course, this condition can be immediately satisfied if one imposes $\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ on ∂E pointwise, as was done in Arbogast [2002, 2004]. However, this pointwise condition does not account for subgrid velocity variability across element interfaces. The important observation (first presented in Juanes [2004]) is that such localization assumption is too stringent and, in fact, unnecessary: all that is required is that the subgrid velocities satisfy the weaker compatibility condition (31).

As a result, we approximate the global subgrid problem (25)–(26) as a set of Neumann problems on individual coarse elements. We make the following observations:

- (1) Since we solve a Neumann problem on each coarse element E , the subgrid velocity test function $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$ must satisfy $\tilde{\mathbf{v}} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ on ∂E , which leads to the following orthogonality condition:

$$(\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}, p_H)_E = 0. \quad (32)$$

- (2) We define the multiscale approximation for the pressure, $W_{H,h} = W_H \oplus \tilde{W}$ such that \tilde{W} is the orthogonal complement of W_H . Since $W_H = \text{div } V_H$, we have the additional orthogonality relation:

$$(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_H, \tilde{p}) = 0 \quad \text{or, equivalently} \quad \int_E \tilde{p} \, d\Omega = 0. \quad (33)$$

This condition guarantees uniqueness of the local subgrid problems.

5.1. The subgrid-scale problem revisited. In the light of the observations above, we define the following functional spaces on the fine grid E_h of each coarse element:

$$\tilde{V}_{E,0} := \{ \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \in RT_0(E_h) : \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \partial E \}, \quad (34)$$

$$\tilde{V}_{E,\tilde{u}} := \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \in RT_0(E_h) : \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \tilde{u}_E \text{ on } \partial E \text{ s.t. } \int_{\partial E} \tilde{u}_E \, d\Gamma = 0 \right\}, \quad (35)$$

$$\tilde{W}_E := \left\{ \tilde{w} \in P_0(E_h) : \int_E \tilde{w} \, d\Omega = 0 \right\}. \quad (36)$$

Using the compatibility condition (31) and the orthogonality conditions (32)–(33), the subgrid problem reads: For each coarse element $E = 1, \dots, N_c$, find $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \tilde{p}) \in \tilde{V}_{E,\tilde{u}} \times \tilde{W}_E$ such that

$$(\tilde{\mathbf{v}}, \mathbf{k}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{u}})_E - (\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}, \tilde{p})_E = -(\tilde{\mathbf{v}}, \mathbf{k}^{-1} \mathbf{u}_H)_E, \quad (37)$$

$$(\tilde{w}, \nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}})_E = (\tilde{w}, f - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_H)_E. \quad (38)$$

for all $\tilde{\mathbf{v}} \in \tilde{V}_{E,0}$ and $\tilde{w} \in \tilde{W}_E$. Given \mathbf{u}_H and the local boundary conditions \tilde{u}_E (to be discussed in Section 6), the problem above has a unique solution. The global subgrid scale solution $(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \tilde{p})$ is then obtained by patching together the solutions on each coarse element, that is, $\tilde{V} = \oplus_E \tilde{V}_{E,\tilde{u}}$ and $\tilde{W} = \oplus_E \tilde{W}_E$.

5.2. The coarse-scale problem revisited. Making use of the compatibility condition (30) and the orthogonality relation (33), the coarse-scale problem reads:

Find $(\mathbf{u}_H, p_H) \in V_H \times W_H$ such that

$$(\mathbf{v}_H, \mathbf{k}^{-1} \mathbf{u}_H) + (\mathbf{v}_H, \mathbf{k}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}) - (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_H, p_H) = -\langle \mathbf{v}_H \cdot \mathbf{n}, \tilde{p} \rangle_{\Gamma_p}, \quad (39)$$

$$(w_H, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_H) = (w_H, f). \quad (40)$$

for all $\mathbf{v}_H \in V_H$ and $w_H \in W_H$. It is interesting to note that the subgrid contribution to the coarse-scale problem, albeit essential, is confined to the second term of Equation (39).

6. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS FOR THE LOCAL SUBGRID PROBLEMS

The description of the method is complete up to the definition of the boundary conditions for the local subgrid problems. They must satisfy the following design conditions:

- (1) Reflect the fine-scale heterogeneity.
- (2) Satisfy the compatibility condition (31).
- (3) Lead to a flux-continuous (conforming) velocity field.
- (4) Have the right magnitude, yet be computable without knowledge of the global velocity field.

In what follows, we shall restrict our attention to the case when $f - \Pi_H f = 0$, that is, when the source/sink term does not present a multiscale character — the treatment of this case is important in the presence of wells and is discussed at length in *Juanes* [2006].

In an attempt to honor condition (4), we scale the subgrid flux across an interface with the overall (coarse) flux across the same interface. This assumption implies the following representation of the multiscale velocity inside a coarse element:

$$\mathbf{u}_{H,h} = \mathbf{u}_H + \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \sum_{a=1}^{n_{\text{face}}} \mathbf{N}_a^H U_a + \sum_{a=1}^{n_{\text{face}}} \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_a U_a, \quad (41)$$

where the index a refers to an element face, \mathbf{N}_a^H are the coarse-scale RT_0 basis functions, and $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_a$ are the subgrid-scale basis functions. Condition (3) will be satisfied as long as the subgrid flux is uniquely defined on the skeleton \mathcal{S}_H of the coarse grid \mathcal{T}_H . An easy way to ensure condition (2) is to satisfy the compatibility condition individually for each interface, which implies that the subgrid-scale basis functions must satisfy:

$$\int_{\Gamma_a} \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_a \cdot \mathbf{n} \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad \forall \Gamma_a \in \mathcal{S}_H. \quad (42)$$

As for condition (1), the subgrid-scale basis functions must be solutions to local problems using the fine-scale permeability \mathbf{k} .

Equation (41) suggests that we express

$$\mathbf{u}_{H,h} = \sum_{a=1}^{n_{\text{face}}} \mathbf{N}_a^{H,h} U_a, \quad (43)$$

where $\mathbf{N}_a^{H,h}$ is the multiscale velocity basis function associated with interface a . Different definitions exist [*Aarnes*, 2004; *Aarnes et al.*, 2005], and in this work we have adopted the recent one proposed by *Kippe et al.* [2006], where the multiscale basis function is the solution to a flow problem restricted to a pair of adjacent coarse elements with source terms specified in such a way that the flow through the interface is identically one (see Figure 1). More precisely, the multiscale basis function $\mathbf{N}_a^{H,h}$ for interface Γ_a (common to coarse elements E_i and E_j) is the solution to the following local problem:

$$\mathbf{k}^{-1} \mathbf{N}_a^{H,h} + \nabla \tilde{\phi}_a = 0 \quad \text{in } E_i \cup E_j, \quad (44)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{N}_a^{H,h} = \begin{cases} w(x) / \int_{E_i} w(x) \, d\Omega & \text{if } x \in E_i, \\ -w(x) / \int_{E_j} w(x) \, d\Omega & \text{if } x \in E_j, \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

$$\mathbf{N}_a^{H,h} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial(E_i \cup E_j). \quad (46)$$

Kippe et al. [2006] suggest to scale the source function with the trace of the permeability tensor, $w(x) = \text{trace } \mathbf{k}(x)$. The local problem (44)–(46) can be solved using a low-order (RT_0) mixed finite element method, or a finite volume method. The subgrid-scale basis function associated with interface Γ_a is then defined as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_a := \mathbf{N}_a^{H,h} - \mathbf{N}_a^H. \quad (47)$$

Clearly, for constant \mathbf{k} , the multiscale basis function reduces to the common RT_0 basis function, and the subgrid basis function is identically equal to zero. In the presence of subgrid heterogeneity, the subgrid basis function will capture not only flow redistribution within the coarse element, but also preferential flow across the interface.

It is easy to show that with this definition of the subgrid basis functions, the velocity field $\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \sum_a \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_a U_a$ and (under appropriate lifting of the basis functions $\tilde{\phi}_a$ on each element) the pressure field $\tilde{p} = \sum_a \tilde{\phi}_a U_a$ is a solution to the subgrid problem (37)–(38).

Figure 1: Diagram illustrating the local flow problem defining the multiscale basis functions.

7. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the variational multiscale mixed finite element method is relatively straightforward (even in the case, not discussed here, when small-scale source terms are present). It consists of the following steps:

- (1) Precompute the subgrid-scale basis functions $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_a$ for each coarse interface Γ_a .
- (2) Build the system of equations corresponding to the coarse-scale problem (39)–(40):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & -\mathbf{B}^t \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U} \\ \mathbf{P} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{g} \\ \mathbf{f} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (48)$$

to be solved for the coarse-scale interface fluxes $\mathbf{U} = \{U_a\}$ and cell-center pressures $\mathbf{P} = \{P_i\}$. The system incorporates the subgrid-scale contributions in matrix \mathbf{A} , obtained by assembly of the coarse-element contributions:

$$A_{ab}^E = \int_E \mathbf{N}_a^H \mathbf{k}^{-1} \mathbf{N}_b^H \, d\Omega + \int_E \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_a^H \mathbf{k}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{N}}_b \, d\Omega. \quad (49)$$

Since both \mathbf{k}^{-1} and $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}_b$ display a multiscale character, the integrals must be evaluated on the underlying fine grid. The matrix is nonsymmetric, reflecting the potential anisotropy induced by correlated subgrid heterogeneity.

- (3) Reconstruct the fine-scale velocity and pressure fields resorting to the additive decomposition (27)–(28). The subgrid part is obtained by linear combination of the (known) coarse-scale fluxes and (precomputed) subgrid-scale basis functions.

8. REPRESENTATIVE NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

In this section, we illustrate the performance of the variational multiscale mixed finite element method in several cases of increasing complexity. We restrict our attention to examples in two dimensions with regular rectangular grids, and in the absence of wells.

8.1. Small channelized system. The first example illustrates the ability of the method to capture the global and detailed flow pattern in the presence of drastic subgrid heterogeneity. The fine grid is just a 4×4 grid, with an isotropic permeability field shown in Figure 2(a). The white blocks are highly conductive ($k = 1$) and the gray blocks correspond to low permeability ($k = 10^{-3}$). Flow is left-to-right, with the left boundary set at a pressure $\bar{p}_{\text{left}} = 1$ and the right boundary at $\bar{p}_{\text{right}} = 0$. The top and bottom boundaries are no-flow boundaries.

The pressure and flux in the x -direction from a finite volume solution computed on the fine grid are shown in Figure 2. The contours of x -flux clearly indicate the preferential flow path along the high-conductivity channel. In Figure 3 we show the solution obtained using the variational multiscale method on a coarse grid of 2×2 elements. Given the sharp contrast in permeability and the fact that there is no scale separation at all (the high-permeability channel spans the entire domain), the multiscale solution is remarkable.

The overall flow rate across the domain is 0.2477, when computed with a refined grid of 16×16 elements. The fine-scale finite volume solution predicts a flow rate of 0.2064 (a 17% error), and the variational multiscale solution a flow rate of 0.1896 (a 23% error).

Figure 2: Small channelized system. Fine-scale finite volume solution.

Figure 3: Small channelized system. Variational multiscale solution on a 2×2 coarse grid.

8.2. Highly heterogeneous, smoothly-varying permeability field. This test case is a two-dimensional problem with a highly heterogeneous (isotropic) permeability. The permeability field, shown in Figure 4(a), has large (but smooth) variations of 6 orders of magnitude. It is taken from the top layer of the 10th SPE comparative solution project [Christie and Blunt, 2001]. The fine grid on which the permeability is defined consists of 60×220 gridblocks. All boundaries are considered to be no-flow boundaries, except for the bottom-left and top-right boundaries, where the pressure is prescribed to $\bar{p}_{\text{bot}} = 100$ and $\bar{p}_{\text{top}} = 0$, respectively (see Figure 4(a)).

The finite volume solution computed on the fine grid is shown in Figure 4. It is apparent that most of the pressure drop occurs at the low permeability region $20 < y < 40$. The contour plots of x - and y -flux clearly indicate flow focusing along the more permeable regions, bypassing the low-permeability areas. The velocity field displays, however, significant small-scale structure in response to the spatial permeability variations. The overall flow rate across the domain computed on the fine grid is 41.55.

In Figure 5 we show the solution (fine-scale pressure, x -flux and y -flux) obtained with the variational multiscale method on a coarse grid of 6×22 elements, each containing 10×10 fine blocks. Despite the large heterogeneity and the rather aggressive 100-fold upgridding, the multiscale solution is remarkably accurate. The overall flow rate computed by the method is 41.27 (a 0.54% error). Moreover, both the large and small scale flow patterns are captured with very high fidelity. It should be noted, however, that even though the average (coarse) pressure field is accurate, the reconstructed (fine) pressure presents slight oscillations at the interfaces between coarse elements.

8.3. Highly heterogeneous, channelized permeability field. The last application example is a challenging two-dimensional problem with a highly heterogeneous, but now rough (channelized) permeability field (see Figure 6(a)). It is a synthetic model of a fluvial reservoir, taken from Layer 59 of the 10th SPE comparative solution project [Christie and Blunt, 2001]. The permeability field is defined again on a fine grid of 60×220 gridblocks. The boundary conditions are the same as in the previous example.

In Figure 6 we plot the pressure and fluxes from a fine-grid finite volume solution. The most salient feature is the pronounced focusing of flow along the high-permeability channels, leading to very high velocities (in both x - and y -directions) over very narrow regions of the domain. This is also true at the inlet and outlet boundaries. The overall flow rate across the domain computed by the finite volume method is 1048.

The variational multiscale solution is shown in Figure 7. It was computed, as before, on a coarse grid of 6×22 elements. The method is able to capture the high-velocity regions very accurately, even though they have a long range in the streamwise direction and a very short range in the spanwise direction. The global flow pattern is reproduced accurately as well. This is evidenced by the computed overall flow rate of 950.2 (a 9.3% error), and also by the recirculation areas that correspond to negative y -flux. Clearly, an essential ingredient of the proposed method is its ability to account for subgrid variability at the element interfaces *and* at the boundaries (see the flow pattern at the top and bottom of Figures 7(c) and (d)). Once again, the multiscale pressure solution agrees well with the fine-grid finite volume solution on an average sense, but presents mild discrepancies after the fine-scale reconstruction step.

Figure 4: Smooth permeability field. Finite volume solution on the fine 60×220 grid.

Figure 5: Smooth permeability field. Variational multiscale solution on a 6×22 grid (10×10 upgridding).

Figure 6: Channelized permeability field. Finite volume solution on the fine 60×220 grid.

Figure 7: Channelized permeability field. Variational multiscale solution on a 6×22 grid (10×10 up-gridding).

9. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The numerical simulations of the previous section demonstrate that the variational multiscale mixed finite element method provides highly accurate solutions to flow scenarios with challenging permeability fields. In the spirit of many other multiscale methods, this is accomplished through the solution of a global coarse-grid problem that incorporates (rigorously, in a variational setting) the effect of the subgrid scales computed locally. The method is an extension of the numerical subgrid upscaling technique proposed by Arbogast [2002] and has clear connection with the multiscale mixed finite element method [Aarnes, 2004]. The key ingredient of our method is a weaker localization assumption of the subgrid problems that allows for subgrid communication across element interfaces and boundaries. The method is locally conservative, conforming, and low-order at both scales.

The method, as presented here, is amenable to a number of extensions, such as:

- (1) Incorporate the effect of small-scale source terms. This issue is essential in the presence of wells, and is treated at length in *Juanes* [2006].
- (2) Enhance the stencil of the velocity approximation by extending the support of the subgrid basis functions to more than two adjacent coarse elements. This extension may prove to be instrumental in capturing focused flow that is misaligned with the coarse grid.
- (3) Incorporate global information in the definition of the local subgrid problems, in the spirit of the coupled local–global upscaling approach of *Chen et al.* [2003].

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